

Steroids and antioxidant activity from *Lantana camara* leaves

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Abstract : Two steroids, namely, 3,15-dihydroxy-cholesterol-21-ene-oic-acid and 3,15,18-trihydroxy-cholesterol-20-ene-oic-acid were isolated from the chloroform extract of *Lantana camara* leaves. The structure of these compounds was identified by usual spectroscopic methods (IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, EI/MS). The antioxidant activity of chloroform extract of *Lantana camara* leaves were determined by three methods viz. DPPH radical assay, hydrogen peroxide assay and reducing power assay. According to these three results, the DPPH method is more significant than that of other two methods. This is first time, to report the steroids present in the chloroform extract of *Lantana camara* leaves.

Keywords : DPPH radical scavenging assay, *Lantana camara*, spectroscopic methods, steroid.

Introduction

Lantana is flowering plants in the verbena family verbenaceae and these plants are cultivated as ornamental. In Tamil language *Lantana camara* is called as 'Unnichedi' and 'Arisimalar'¹. The *Lantana* name was originated from Late Latin, where it refers to *Viburnum Lantana*. *Lantana camara* extracts were used for protection of Cabbage against the aphid *Lipaphis erysimi*². The *Lantana camara* leaves are used in treatment of rheumatism, tumors, itches, cuts, ulcers, swellings, tetanus and reported to possess carminative, antiseptic, diaphoretic properties³. Phytochemicals with antioxidant activity is the major contributor to reduce the risk of cancer and improve heart health. *Lantana camara* was expansively investigated for the phytochemical compositions, alkaloids, steroids; terpenoids are reported as major chemical constituents of *Lantana camara*. In India, many research being done on the antimicrobial, antifungal activity of leaf extracts of *Lantana camara*⁴. *Lantana camara* flowers are used in coconut oil provides protection from *Aedes* mosquitoes⁵. With this background, the present study was to isolate steroids and evaluate the antioxidant activity of chloroform extract of *Lantana camara* leaves.

Materials and methods :

Collection, identification and preparation of plant materials :

The leaves of the plant *Lantana camara* collected nearby Government Arts College in Thanjavur district and authenticated by Dr. John Britto, Rapinet Herbarium, St. Joseph's College, Tiruchirappalli. The leaves were cleaned with tap water and dried in shadow and then using pulverizer to crush into powder.

Extraction :

The powdered sample was extracted with 95% ethanol by using cold method extraction in room temperature for one week, and then it was filtered, distilled and concentrated to obtain the solid greenish residue. The 95% ethanol extract was further fractionated with petroleum ether, *n*-hexane, chloroform, ethyl acetate, ethanol, *n*-butanol and methanol. The solvents were recovered under reduced pressure.

Isolation :

5 g of chloroform soluble part was subjected to column chromatography using 60-120 silica gel mesh, that was packed using wet packing method in hexane with

increasing polarity of hexane to chloroform (100, 75 : 25, 50 : 50, 25 : 75, 100). From that 50% and 25% hexane fraction was recrystallized with methanol to obtained white color solid amorphous powder compound-1 (42 mg) and compound-2 (65) which was analyzed by spectroscopic studies. This was identified by spectral studies.

General experimental procedures :

FT-IR (Fourier Transform-Infra red) spectra were obtained using Perkin-Elmer FT-IR 450-4000 in KBr disc and absorption peaks in terms of wave numbers (cm^{-1}). EI-MS (electron impact mass spectrum) were recorded on Jeol instrument. NMR (Nuclear magnetic resonance) was acquired on Bruker at 300 MHz (^1H) and 100 MHz (^{13}C). Chemical shifts were recorded as δ value (ppm), chloroform as an inert solvent.

Antioxidant activity :

Antioxidant capacity was determined using known methods⁹⁻¹¹.

Results and discussion

Compound 1 :

The compound 1 is a white amorphous powder. In IR spectra the absorption appeared at 3448 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of OH group and the signal present in 2976 cm^{-1} , 1387 cm^{-1} , 1236 cm^{-1} due to presence of CH_3 and CH_2 group respectively. The signal at 1110 cm^{-1} , 1641 cm^{-1} due to $\text{C}=\text{O}$ group and $\text{C}=\text{C}$ group. The proton NMR gave the signal at δ ppm 1.25 (H-1), 1.58 (H-2), 3.6 (H-3 attached with OH group), 1.46 (H-4), 1.47 (H-5), 4.19 (H-15), 1.06 (H-19), 1.9 (H-20), 7.71 (H-21), 7.51 (H-22), 1.03 (H-24). ^{13}C NMR shows peak at δ ppm 27.37 (C-1), 30.9 (C-2), 68.08 (C-3), 37.13 (C-5), 27.4 (C-6), 22.7 (C-7), 45.3 (C-9), 37.1 (C-10), 22.7 (C-11), 32.8 (C-13), 43.5 (C-14), 61.2 (C-15), 19.72 (C-19), 37.1 (C-20), 122.57 (C-21), 142.7 (C-22), 177 (C-23), 20.4 (C-24). The molecular ion peak of isolated steroid exhibited at m/z 391. Based on the above deliberation and by comparing with other similar compounds⁶, the structure of the isolated compound is given in Fig. 1.

Compound 2 :

The compound 2 is a white amorphous powder. In IR spectra shows absorption band at 3448 (OH bond), 2976 (CH_3 group), 2858 (CH_2 group), 1728 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$ of an acid),

Fig. 1. Structure of isolated steroids.

1459, 1387 (CH_3 , CH_2 group), 1276 (alcoholic group), 1124 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$ group). The proton NMR gave the signal at δ ppm 1.36 (H-1), 1.56 (H-2), 3.5 (H-3 attached with OH group), 1.5 (H-4), 1.47 (H-5-14), 4.03 (H-15), 4.2 (H-18), 2.5 (H-19), 7.6 (H-20), 7.4 (H-21), 1.06 (H-23). The mass spectra of the present compound exhibited a molecular ion peak at m/z 393 and fragmented peaks at m/z 376, 347, 222, 195, 180, 148, 124, 110. Based on above investigation and by comparing with other similar compounds⁵⁻⁸, the proposed structure of the isolated compound is given in Fig. 1.

Antioxidant activity :

The antioxidant activity showed the inhibition percentage is 59.36%, 42.53% and 14.20% respectively.

Table 1. Antioxidant activity of chloroform extract of *Lantana camara* leaves

Sr. no.	Method	Percentage of antioxidant activity	Standard (BHT) (0.01 mg/ml)
1.	DPPH assay	59.36	78.74
2.	Reducing power assay	42.53	69.72
3.	Hydrogen peroxide assay	14.20	45.92

The results observed from chloroform extract of *Lantana camara* leaves shows higher antioxidant potential and compared to three methods, DPPH assay observed high antioxidant activity. The results were compared to the standard BHT, it was only slight difference has been noted. The WHO estimated that 80% of the population of developing countries still depends on traditional medicine, mostly plant drugs for their primary health care needs. Hence, there is an urgent need to study the screening of antioxidant properties of herbs which will be helpful in the treatment of several diseases⁹⁻¹¹.

Conclusion

This is the first time, to report the steroids present in the chloroform extract of *Lantana camara* leaves. The pharmacological studies of above compounds were work-in progress. In future, the analysis by the different solvent system one could congregate to find novel compounds present in the plant. On the basis of our results, *Lantana camara* appears to have potential for treatment of oxidative stress related diseases. It should, however, be explored as a functional medicinal plant for isolating the active ingredients along with animal studies *in vivo*.

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